

The Life and Work of Abu'l-Barakat Hibat Allah ibn Malka al-Baghdadi, Physician-Philosopher and Physicist

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Abstract: This paper aims to retrace the main biographical milestones of Abū l-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī based on available sources, highlighting understudied aspects. It also presents the complete body of his works, identifying their philosophical and scientific dimensions. To our knowledge, there is to date no comprehensive synthesis of the scholarship dedicated to this author. This article fills that gap by offering, for the first time, a critical and structured overview of the entire secondary literature, while advancing an original hypothesis concerning his biography, the absence of known teachers, and his intellectual legacy. In this preliminary version, emphasis is placed on the current state of previous research, critically assessed within a literature review framework, in order to provide a coherent overall picture while laying the groundwork for more in-depth future developments.

Résumé : Le présent article se propose de retracer les principaux jalons biographiques d'Abū l-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī à partir des sources disponibles, en mettant en lumière des éléments peu étudiés. Il présente également l'ensemble de ses œuvres, en identifiant les axes philosophiques et scientifiques. À notre connaissance, il n'existe à ce jour aucune synthèse exhaustive des travaux consacrés à cet auteur. Cet article comble cette lacune en offrant pour la première fois un état des lieux critique et structuré de l'ensemble de la littérature secondaire, tout en avançant une hypothèse inédite concernant sa biographie, l'absence de maîtres, et ces œuvres. Dans cette version préliminaire, l'accent est porté sur l'état actuel des travaux antérieurs mis en perspective dans le cadre d'une revue de la littérature, afin d'offrir une vue d'ensemble cohérente, tout en préparant des développements plus approfondis dans le futur.

Keywords: Dynamics of motion, time, impetus, philosophy, Metaphysics, astronomy.

1 Introduction

The figure of Abū al-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī (c. 1077–1164), nicknamed Awḥad al-Zamān (“the unique of his time”), remains one of the most fascinating figures of the XIIth-century Muslim intellectual world. A philosopher, physician, physicist, and commentator on the Torah, he was born in Baghdad into a Jewish family under the name Baruch ben Malka. His education took place in a historical context where Greek philosophy, notably that of Aristotle, had already been translated, assimilated, and

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developed in the Islamic world by major figures such as Abū Yūsuf Ya‘qūb ibn Ishāq al-Kindī (801–873), al-Fārābī (872–950), and Ibn Sīnā (Avicenna) (980–1037). Unlike his predecessors and contemporaries, Abū’l-Barakāt did not limit himself to commenting on or extending Avicennian thought : he developed a profoundly original body of work, among which the Kitāb al-Mu’tabar fī al-ḥikma stands as its most accomplished expression. This work serves both as a critical synthesis and a reevaluation of the foundations of natural philosophy and metaphysics inherited from the Greeks, as well as of so-called philosophical physics. His approach, based on an original observation he terms “Itibār,” allowed him to propose advances in kinematics, dynamics, time, and space. These contributions position Abū’l-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī as a pivotal figure between the Peripatetic tradition² and the precursors of Newtonian theory, particularly regarding acceleration, inertia, and momentum.

The study of this scholar, close to the sultans and the Abbasid caliphate, offers dual scientific significance. On the one hand, it illuminates the intellectual debates of the late Abbasid period and the specificity of Baghdadi rationalism. On the other hand, it contributes to a better understanding of the evolution of physics and metaphysics at the height of Muslim civilization, revealing unexpected conceptual continuities with medieval Latin thought. Finally, Abū’l-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī’s conversion to Islam—a subject of historiographical debate—adds a singular dimension to his intellectual trajectory. Far from being the result of coercion, it appears to be part of a path of mature philosophical and spiritual reflection.

This article is part of the ongoing research devoted to the life and works of Abū al-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī, advancing new insights concerning his education and intellectual environment.

1.1 Objectifs this article

The present study pursues two main objectives :

2. Aristotelianism in the narrow sense refers strictly to Aristotle, whereas “Peripateticism” designates the broader philosophical current that followed the master. The term “radical Aristotelianism” is sometimes used to denote Latin Averroism in contrast with Thomism.

1. **Biography** : This section aims to establish, on the basis of the sources currently available, the principal biographical milestones of Abū l-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī. This investigation has made it possible to identify several elements which, to our knowledge, have hitherto been neither the subject of a systematic analysis nor placed within a historiographical perspective.
2. **Works** : A presentation of the works is proposed, highlighting the principal philosophical and scientific axes that structure them. Within the framework of this preliminary version of the article (prepublication), particular emphasis is deliberately placed on the current state of research : previous studies are surveyed, synthesized, and critically contextualized through a literature review, with the aim of offering a coherent and well-informed overview of the field, while preparing the ground for more in-depth future developments.

Positioning of the article. This article does not seek to replace the specialized studies already devoted to Ibn Malkā ; rather, it distinguishes itself through a dual original contribution :

1. **An interpretative advance** : A new hypothesis concerning the biographical and intellectual gaps surrounding Ibn Malkā-most notably the scarcity of disciples-will be developed, thus offering a renewed explanation for these historiographical “blind spots”.
2. **A comprehensive synthesis** : For the first time, the entirety of the available scholarship (primary sources, manuscripts, studies in Arabic and Western languages) is brought together in the form of a critical *state of the art*, providing a complete and structured overview of current research.

Thus, the value of this article lies less in the discovery of previously unknown sources than in the combination of a stimulating hypothetical proposal and a systematic survey of existing knowledge, intended to serve as a reference point for future studies.

1.2 Organization of the Article

Section 2 is devoted to the life of Abū al-Barakāt Hibat Allāh Ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī, providing a biographical synthesis and outlining the religious, political, and scientific context in which he lived; it also establishes a bibliography of his students. Section 3 presents his works—primarily his magnum opus, Kitāb al-Mu'tabar—and analyzes his conceptual contributions to physics, metaphysics, and psychology within the texts that have come down to us. Finally, Section 4 concludes the article.

2 Overview of the Life of Abū al-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī

Abū al-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī—known in Arab-Muslim historiography as Ibn Malkā, a name derived from his Hebrew patronymic Nathaniel ben Malkā—was dubbed "Awḥad al-Zamān" (the "Unique of his Age") by his contemporaries. He was likely born between 480 and 560 AH (approximately 1087–1165 AD) in Baghdad [B94], which was then the intellectual center of the Islamic world. As a philosopher, physician, and physicist, he stands as one of the most prominent figures of 12th-century rational thought. His work is distinguished by the richness of its synthesis between Greek heritage, medical knowledge, and metaphysical reflection. Several historians of science and philosophy, such as Ibn Abī Uṣaybi'a, Ibn al-Qifṭī, and al-Bayhaqī [Ba46], have described him as an original, innovative, independent, and critical mind.

Some contemporary historians of science have proposed approximate dates situating the birth and death of Abū al-Barakāt between 480 and 560 AH (1087–1165 AD). At the time, he was known to the general public by the nickname al-Baladī, referring to Balad, a small town near Mosul whose ruins are identified today as Eski Mosul or "Balad" in Arabic. However, some sources diverge regarding his birthplace; for instance, the Jewish Encyclopedia, published between 1901 and 1906, suggests that he was born in al-Baṣra rather than Balad.

Teachers and Early Trainings. A crucial element in the scholarly trajectory of Abū al-Barakāt Hibat Allāh Ibn Malkā lies in the formative—yet decisive—phase of his intellectual and medical education. However, the available sources that have come down to us preserve almost no trace of his teachers, with the exception of a single name explicitly mentioned. In this regard, an anecdote reported by several chroniclers refers to one of his instructors in medicine :

[...] At that time, the great scholar of Basra, Abū al-Ḥasan ibn Hibat Allāh, had established a rule forbidding Jews from attending his lectures, although they were numerous in the region (their number reportedly reaching approximately 25,000 in the Iraqi city). This prohibition made Abū al-Barakāt's intellectual path particularly difficult. Nevertheless, his ardent desire for knowledge led him to listen to the lessons secretly, from behind the walls. Admiring his perseverance and his thirst for learning, Abū al-Ḥasan eventually accepted him among his disciples [...]

This anecdote raises several questions concerning the very existence, identity, and role of the teachers under whom Abū al-Barakāt may have received his education. The surviving sources mention almost none, a silence that stands in sharp contrast to the diversity, depth, and originality of his intellectual contributions. In a scholarly tradition in which even a modest student was typically trained under at least two recognized masters, this absence of documentation raises more questions than it provides answers.

His Conversion to Islam. Historians of science and religion have emphasized the ambiguities surrounding the conversion of Abū al-Barakāt Hibat Allāh Ibn Malkā to Islam, which have given rise to sustained controversy and a wide range of hypotheses. Sylvie Nony, for her part, underscores the scarcity and, at times, the contradictory nature of the sources available for this crucial phase of his life [No10]. Medieval historians such as 'a and Ibn al-Qifṭī generally report that Abū al-Barakāt converted to Islam in the final years of his life, at which point he adopted the name “al-Mutakallim,” a view later followed by the eminent scholar and historian al-Dhahabī [Al01]. By contrast, other scholars question the authenticity of this conversion, portraying it as coerced and motivated by social or political pressure. These accounts emphasize that Abū al-Barakāt may have privately retained certain heterodox philosophical

convictions, without fully adhering to Islamic theological dogma. A third hypothesis advances sociological and economic arguments, suggesting that the conversion served primarily to preserve his social status and proximity to the Abbasid caliphal court.

The Circumstances of His Death. The account of the circumstances surrounding his death is reported by two historians, Ibn al-Qiftī and Ibn Khallikān (1172–1248) : “He was afflicted with leprosy and treated himself by applying to his body snakes that he had previously starved. They bit him excessively, but he recovered from the leprosy— though he became blind. It appears, however, that he later regained his eyesight” [Kh94]. He died in Hamadān at approximately eighty years of age, and his coffin was subsequently transported to Baghdad.

Abū al-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī requested that an inscription be placed on his tomb. In her doctoral dissertation, Sylvie Nony summarizes the divergence among sources concerning the date of his death : several accounts indicate that his death coincided with that of Sultan Mas’ūd. Since the date of the latter is precisely known, these sources agree in placing Ibn Malkā’s death in 547/1152.

2.1 The Students of Abū al-Barakāt Ibn Malka

Despite a long life, estimated to have lasted between eighty and ninety years (Tayyeb [Ta80]), Abū al-Barakāt Ibn Malka enjoyed remarkable success : his vast renown, his eminent social standing, his prestige at the courts of the Seljuk sultans and Abbasid caliphs, as well as his personal wealth, all attest to his exceptional status. Yet, paradoxically, he seems to have had relatively few disciples—contrary to the widespread custom of the time, which saw scholars, physicians, and philosophers surrounded by a significant circle of students. Extant sources mention only a very small number of them, barely evoking one notable disciple in medicine ; furthermore, no student of the Jewish faith appears to have followed Abū al-Barakāt’s teaching. This absence remains all the more surprising given that the scholar himself dedicated several writings and reflections to the Torah—works which, as

Shlomo Pines pointed out, do not seem to have been transmitted through direct instruction.

'Abd al-Latīf al-Baghdādī. 'Abd al-Laṭīf al-Baghdādī (Muwaffaq al-Dīn Abū Muḥammad ibn Yūsuf) (1162–1231) was an eminent Arab physician, historian, and polymath, born and deceased in Baghdad. His academic career led him to teach philosophy and medicine in Cairo and Damascus for several years, as well as in Aleppo for a briefer period. Among the vast corpus (primarily medical) attributed to him by Ibn Abī Uṣaybi'a, only his work titled *Al-Ifāda wa-l-I'tibār* (commonly known as *Description of Egypt*) appears to have survived. This work is considered a pioneering study in Egyptian antiquities. In it, al-Baghdādī provides a detailed account of the famine that occurred in Egypt (circa 1200–1202) during his stay, caused by an insufficient rise of the Nile. He recounts having had, in this context, "the opportunity to observe and examine a large number of skeletons." This systematic osteological observation—one of the first documented of its kind—allowed him to empirically refute certain claims made by Galen, notably regarding the anatomy of the mandible (which he demonstrated to be a single bone) and the sacrum. The work also contains detailed descriptions of ancient monuments. Furthermore, al-Baghdādī relays the account attributing the destruction of the Library of Alexandria to Caliph 'Umar ibn al-Khaṭṭāb, who allegedly ordered his general 'Amr ibn al-'Āṣ to destroy it in 642. His final years were marked by travels to Armenia and Asia Minor. He died in Baghdad upon his return from (or during the preparations for) a pilgrimage to Mecca.

2.1.1 Putative Disciples of Abū al-Barakāt Ibn Malka

This section is devoted to the putative students of Abū al-Barakāt Ibn Malka. The aim here is to address hypothetical disciples whose existence cannot be confirmed with certainty. It is important to emphasize that this approach does not stem from modern speculation : in many historical cases, the identification of students relies on temporal, geographical, or disciplinary coincidences, as well as on correlations between fields of expertise and chronological

intervals. It is on this basis that we designate certain individuals as likely disciples.

Hasan 'Alī ibn Ahmad ibn Habal. Muhaddhib al-Dīn Abū al-Hasan 'Alī ibn Ahmad ibn Habal, born in Baghdad around 1122 and deceased in 1213, was an eminent Arab physician and scholar. Although a native of Baghdad, the bulk of his medical and intellectual career took place in Mosul (Northern Iraq), where he composed his major works. His legacy rests primarily on his medical compendium entitled *Kitāb al-Mukhtārāt fī al-ṭibb* (The Book of Selections in Medicine). This work was completed in 1165, a date that coincides with the death of Abū al-Barakāt Ibn Malkā. This systematic opus synthesizes a vast corpus of medical knowledge from the Greco-Arabic tradition (notably Galen and Hippocrates) and authors of the Islamic era, such as Ibn Sīnā (Avicenna). Distinguishing itself from Avicenna's *Qānūn fī al-ṭibb* (Canon), which was designed as an exhaustive encyclopedic work, Ibn Habal's *Mukhtārāt* is characterized by its selective approach and practical aim, addressing both scholars and practitioners. The work covers pathology, etiology (causes), and symptomatology, as well as pharmacological and dietary remedies, offering selections of proven prescriptions. The *Kitāb al-Mukhtārāt* acquired considerable influence in the medical circles of Mosul and Baghdad. It bears witness to the vitality of medicine in the 12th-century Islamic world, demonstrating that physicians of this period did not limit themselves to compiling ancient knowledge, but actively reinterpreted and adapted it to the requirements of contemporary practice. Ibn Habal's work thus illustrates the role of Baghdad and Mosul as major centers of transmission and innovation in medieval Arab-Islamic medicine.

The Case of Ibn Yaḥyā al-Maghribī al-Samaw'al. Al-Samaw'al al-Maghribī (Samu'il ibn Yaḥyā al-Maghribī) was an emblematic 12th-century scholar, mathematician, and physician. His trajectory presents a notable analogy to that of Abū al-Barakāt Ibn Malkā : both were eminent scholars of Jewish origin who converted to Islam. The master-student relationship between al-Samaw'al and Ibn Malkā has been proposed, notably by Sylvie Nony [No12]. This connection is based on geographical convergence : *al-Samaw'al conducted a scientific tour in Iraq, where Ibn Malkā resided*

and practiced (the latter having, according to sources, rarely or never left Iraq). However, this direct lineage remains hypothetical. While al-Samaw' al may have been influenced by Ibn Malkā's work or by the intellectual and polemical climate of the era—illustrated by contemporaries such as Muwaffaq al-Dīn al-Baghdādī (author of a Refutation of the Jews)—he does not mention Ibn Malkā as his master. Moreover, in his autobiography (Iḥām al-Yahūd, "The Confutation of the Jews"), al-Samaw' al emphasizes the rational and endogenous nature of his conversion. He asserts that his decision was the result of "reflection, meditation, and careful examination" of doctrines, leading him to the "irrefutable demonstration" of his new conviction. Al-Samaw' al takes care to specify that he only revealed the dreams he had (involving the Prophet Samuel and the Prophet Muhammad) four years after his conversion. He thus aimed to demonstrate that his adherence to Islam stemmed from a rational inquiry and a thorough comparison of religions, rather than from a dreamlike impulse or external influence

Remark 1 *(The Case of Fakhr al-Dīn al-Rāzī) It is necessary to dispel a confusion regarding the relationship between Ibn Malkā and Fakhr al-Dīn al-Rāzī. Certain writings insinuate that al-Rāzī was a disciple of Abū al-Barakāt Ibn Malkā. This claim is chronologically untenable : Abū al-Barakāt died (circa 1165) before or around the birth of al-Rāzī (circa 1149–1150; the exact date being debated, he was but a child at the time of Ibn Malkā's death). While al-Rāzī extensively studied, criticized, and commented upon Ibn Malkā's philosophical and scientific work (notably the Kitāb al-Mu'tabar), this can only be understood as an intellectual lineage. It is impossible for him to have been his student in the sense of direct instruction, unless the term is employed metaphorically to designate one who profoundly studies the writings of a previous master.*

3 The Works of Abū'l-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī

Historians and chroniclers agree in regarding *Kitāb al-Mu'tabar fī al-Hikmā* (The Book of What Is Established through Personal Reflection [on

Wisdom]) as his masterpiece. Ibn Abī Uṣaybi‘a [Us66] highlights *Kitāb al-Mu’tabar fī al-Hikma* as the principal and most renowned among his writings. Nevertheless, although this work occupies a central place in the scientific life of Abū’l-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī, it does not constitute his sole contribution (Table ??)³. Like most scholars of his time, he also composed treatises in medicine and astronomy, as well as in metaphysics, which appears to be more recent than *Kitāb al-Mu’tabar fī al-Hikma*. It should be noted that these works have come down to us in varying states of preservation.

3.1 State of Research on *Kitāb al-Mu’tabar fī al-Hikma*

In the Arab-Islamic world, *Kitāb al-Mu’tabar fī al-Hikma* by Abū al-Barakāt Ibn Malkā attracted considerable attention from the time of its circulation. The work was noted both for the depth of its philosophical theses and for its use of arguments drawn from *kalām*, which in particular elicited the critical interest of Ibn Taymiyya, as several recent studies have pointed out [Al24]. This early reception testifies to the distinctive place the work already occupied within the Muslim intellectual landscape.

Interest in the *Mu’tabar* has been significantly renewed in contemporary scholarship. Modern studies have focused primarily on the sections devoted to natural philosophy—often identified as Parts II and III of the work—emphasizing Ibn Malkā’s innovative theories of time, space, *mayl* (impetus), and dynamics. By contrast, while the philosophical and physical dimensions of the work (Volumes I and II) have been the subject of substantial analysis, Ibn Malkā’s medical corpus—whether embedded in certain sections of the *Mu’tabar* or developed in independent treatises—remains, to date, relatively understudied and has not benefited from a comparable level of critical scrutiny.

3. The list of the scientific works of Abū’l-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī deserves to be updated.

Three Volumes of *Kitāb al-Mu'tabar fī al-Ḥikma* :

- The first volume is devoted to logic.
- The second volume is dedicated to the natural sciences (physics, astronomy).
- The third volume is devoted to metaphysics.

Remark 2 *It is appropriate to pause here in order to clarify the understanding of the title of this major work. The usual translation of the central term al-I'tibār as “reflection” remains subject to debate. As Sylvie Nony suggests in her dissertation [No10], the semantic field of al-I'tibār goes beyond mere intellectual speculation : the term is closer to “contemplation,” or more precisely to “teaching,” understood as the lesson derived from observation or experience. In this sense, al-I'tibār does not refer to passive meditation but to a form of active knowledge aimed at developing operational conclusions.*

This epistemological orientation sheds, at least in part, light on another remarkable feature of the work. Indeed, as Ibn al-Qifī reports, the Kitāb al-Mu'tabar is presented as “free from any kind of mathematics,” a singularity that constitutes a notable exception compared with the scholarly practices of his time. Far from reflecting a gap or accidental disinterest, this absence can be interpreted as consistent with the intellectual project of the work : Ibn Malkā favors a form of knowledge based on qualitative analysis, experience, and rational argumentation, rather than on mathematical formalization, thus situating his work within an original philosophical approach to the natural sciences of the medieval period.

In the West, the works of Abū al-Barakāt Ibn Malkā have also attracted significant academic interest. This interest was largely initiated by the foundational studies of Shlomo Pines, which played a decisive role in introducing his thought within modern philosophical and historical studies, as notably emphasized by Sylvie Nony [No11]. Pines' contributions [Pi79a; Pi79b; Pi79c; Pi79d; Pi79e] paved the way for structured and interdisciplinary research on Ibn Malkā.

TABLE 1 : Summary of Ibn Malkā's Publications (after Nony, 2010)

Title	Manuscript References	Edition	Translation	Genre
<i>Kitāb al-Mu'tabar fī al-Ḥikma I,II,III</i>	Istanbul : Lāleli 2553 (I, IV, 564h), Es'ad Efendi 1931 (I-IV, 744h), Fātih 3224 (IV, 595h), 3225 (III), 3226 (IV), Köprulu 919 (I, 564h), Fazil Ahmed Pacha 919 (I, 700h), Cairo, Dār al-Kutub : Cairo 4451 (I.6 to I.8, II, III.1 and III.2), Cairo 4452 (III continuation and end)	Arabic edition Haydarābād 1938	Turkish translation of the metaphysics section <i>Ilāhiyat</i> (Badat) for (Ebulberekāt) philosopher (<i>Kitābül-meteber</i>) third part	I : Philosophy, II : Physics, III : Medicine
<i>Risāla fī sabab zuhūr al-kawākib laylan wa ihtifā'ihā nahāran</i> (Epistle on the Cause of the Nocturnal Appearance of the Stars and Their Diurnal Disappearance)	Berlin 5671, Istanbul Ayasofya 4832/13 – Qatar – UK	Edited : 2022		Astronomy ⁴
<i>Siyāsāt al-badan wa fādīlat al-šarāb wa manāfi'uhū wa madārruhū</i> (The Regimen of the Body and the Merits, Benefits, and Harms of Drink)	Contextualized in terms of the discipline			Medicine
<i>Ihtisār Kitāb al-Tašrīh</i> (Summary of Galen's Anatomy Book)				Summary of a surgery treatise
<i>Šarḥ siḡr al-šāmi'a</i> (Commentary on Ecclesiastes)	Oxford, Bodleian, Hebr. fonds no. 131[Hi35]		- Written in Judeo-Arabic; some Jewish passages translated by Pines	Jewish theology/philosophy
<i>Kitāb saḡīḡ adīllat al-naql fī māhiyyat al-'aql</i> (Authentic Scriptural Data on the Quiddity of the Intellect)	Leipzig 882/1 fol. 1-17 ms. dated 552/1157	Scientific edition in Arabic and French commentary by A. al-Tayyib, <i>Ann. Isl.</i> 80		Philosophical treatise
<i>Šiḡat Barša'ā</i> (Description of the Barša'tā)	Three manuscripts of this work referenced in Turkish libraries			Pharmacology treatise
<i>Tiryāq amīr al-arwāḡ</i> (The Antidote of the Prince of Souls)	ms. 1781, folios 157b-159a, Kitapsaray Library, Manisa, Turkey			Pharmacology treatise
<i>Risāla fī al-naḡs</i> (Epistle on the Soul)	Arabic Manuscripts Institute no. 4855			Philosophy
<i>Risāla fī al-qadā' wa-l-qadar</i> (Epistle on Destiny and Predestination)				Philosophy
<i>Risāla fī al-'amal bi-'l-šafīḡha al-'āḡāḡiyyah</i> (Epistle on the Universal Tympanum of the Astrolabe)	Niğde, Turkey			Astronomy
<i>Hawāšī 'alā kitāb al-qānūn fī al-tibb</i> (Commentaries on Avicenna's <i>Canon of Medicine</i>)	Mentioned by G. R. Sidbī			Medicine

Contemporary research today revolves around several major disciplinary axes : metaphysics, philosophy, logic, and physics. In this regard, two areas stand out particularly :

1. **Physics and Logic.** Ibn Malkā's physics—sometimes referred to as the "physics of philosophical reflection"—has attracted sustained interest, notably due to his innovative concepts regarding time, space, and motion. His works in logic have also drawn attention, particularly for their critical stance towards the Aristotelian tradition.
2. **Metaphysics.**
3. **Medicine.** Conversely, his specifically medical writings remain relatively marginal in the current academic landscape, despite their potential importance for the history of medieval medicine.

The academic corpus has also been enriched by studies in Arabic, particularly from the Egyptian university milieu, focusing on his psychological writings. Major monographs have likewise been dedicated to him [Fr18 ; Pa17]. Other works explore specific philosophical themes [Ab93 ; Sa05 ; Sa20 ; TK21] or situate Ibn Malkā's thought within a comparative framework, notably in relation to that of Fakhr al-Dīn al-Rāzī [Gr11]. Finally, recent critical reappraisals [Gr18] contribute to an ongoing reevaluation of his intellectual legacy.

3.2 Physics

The works of Sylvie Nony represent a major contribution to the study of Abū al-Barakāt Ibn Malkā's physics [No10 ; No11 ; No12]. Through an analysis now considered classical—often titled "The Dynamics of Abū al-Barakāt : Creating the Void to Think Change"—Nony examines the philosopher's conceptions of space, the void, and motion. She highlights Ibn Malkā's hypothetical acceptance of the existence of the void and shows that his explicit departure from Aristotelian dynamics constitutes a significant conceptual break. This position, far from being a mere internal variation within Peripatetic thought, can be interpreted as a partial anticipation of

FIGURE 1 : ms. Es'ad Efendi ([No10])

FIGURE 2 : ms. Fatih 3224([No10])

certain later developments in modern physics from the sixteenth century onwards.

These analyses are part of a broader body of research dedicated to Ibn Malkā's physical thought, notably complemented by the works of [Ma10; Sa96]. Targeted studies on the concept of motion have also been conducted, particularly by Iranian scholars [ES12; Ha17]. More broadly, the current state of research also includes the contributions of Janssens [Ja16; Ja18a; Ja18b], as well as those of [Ha07; KK17; Y120].

3.3 Kitāb saḥīḥ adillat al-naql fī māhiyyat al-'aql (The Authentic Scriptural Data on the Quiddity of the Intellect or Treatise on the Intellect)

Abū al-Barakāt al-Baghdādī's treatise, *Kitāb Ṣaḥīḥ Adillat al-Naql fī Māhiyyat al-'Aql*, reveals the significance of the evolving debates on the nature of the intellect [Ta80], situated at the core of *ilm al-Kalām* and Islamic philosophy, initiated primarily by Ḥarīth al-Muhāsibī (781–857) in his book *Fāham al-Qur'ān wa Ma'īyyāt al-'Aql* [Al21; Mu71], well before the 12th century. Abū al-Barakāt al-Baghdādī articulates an original position that seeks to transcend both classical Aristotelianism and Avicennian systematization in a novel manner, integrating arguments derived from scriptural transmission (*naql*) with those based on rational demonstration.

By situating this treatise within the broader framework of *ilm al-Kalām* discussions on the intellect, along with the knowledge and cognitive faculties it generates, Ahmed Tayyib's work demonstrates that Abū al-Barakāt al-Baghdādī develops an original epistemology of revelation, thereby breaking with strictly Peripatetic approaches. This approach endows his thought with remarkable autonomy, allowing these commentaries to be regarded as a new philosophical path. The treatise highlights the significant interest in preserving a philosophical tradition distinct from the major dominant currents of his time, both within Islamic philosophy and medieval Jewish thought.

3.4 **Risāla fī sabab zuhūr al-kawākib laylan wa ihtifā'ihā nahāran** (**Epistle on the Cause of the Nocturnal Appearance of the Stars and Their Diurnal Disappearance**)

The epistle on the cause of the nocturnal appearance of the stars and their diurnal disappearance was recently studied and published by Hala Mahdjoub [Mo22].

Remark 3 *This is an astronomical treatise on the cause of the appearance of planets on certain nights and their disappearance. This treatise was presented by Abū al-Barakāt Hibat Allāh to the Seljuk Sultan Muḥammad Tapar ibn Malikshāh, who reigned between 1105 and 1118 CE. The copy currently available is not the original : it was recopied in the 17th century, and only five pages remain (figure 3).*

Context. Abū al-Barakāt al-Baghdādī approached the study of this question in response to what he had learned from his predecessors, who claimed that the light of the Sun, by its brilliance, would render the planets invisible when it is present (figure 4). Abū al-Barakāt al-Baghdādī then questioned the mechanism of this apparent disappearance. He noted that previous authors asserted that if the rays of the Sun reached only half of the celestial sphere and the Earth, and if the Earth were the same size as the Sun, it could not obscure the Sun's light over the entire half of the sky, but only over a limited portion of the solar disc.

Hence a new question arises : how could such a phenomenon be possible, given that the ancients maintained that the Sun's size far exceeded that of the Earth's sphere, being several times larger? Abū al-Barakāt al-Baghdādī faced a conceptual difficulty : how could the Earth—clearly much smaller than the Sun—produce a perceptible occultation of a portion of the sky? This apparent contradiction became the starting point of his reflection in this treatise.

FIGURE 3 : First folio of the manuscript. *Risāla fī sabab zuhūr al-kawākib laylan wa ihtifā' ihā nahāran* (Qatar⁵)

FIGURE 4 : Abū al-Barakāt al-Baghdādī's Assessment of Ancient Theories of Visionī

4 Conclusion

Although much work remains to be done in order to examine in detail the theoretical, logical, and philosophical aspects of the contributions of Abū al-Barakāt al-Baghdādī (Ibn Malkā) in philosophy, physics, metaphysics, and logic, the originality of his works remains indisputable and attests to the remarkable qualities of this scholar-physician. Nevertheless, these contributions raise a number of questions : some can now be addressed on the basis of the source material currently available, while others still call for further research grounded in documents that have come down to us, a large part of which has not yet been subjected to in-depth investigation despite existing publications. In this conclusion, we shall confine ourselves to presenting three of these questions.

The first question concerns the scientific milieu and its social structure in which Ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī grew up and was trained. However brilliant his personal abilities may have been, they could neither have emerged nor developed without a set of favorable conditions, first brought together in his place of origin-whose identification remains a matter of debate-where a sufficiently structured system of instruction must have existed, and later within the various centers to which he traveled in order to pursue his education

under specialized teachers. Such a trajectory necessarily implies the existence of active scholarly communities, more or less extensive in scope, as well as the maintenance of regular channels of knowledge circulation among their members.

Yet the available research remains too fragmentary to move beyond the level of hypothesis, being based primarily on the study of the individual itineraries of a few contemporary scholars and on the testimonies partial in themselves left to us by the major metropolitan centers of the Abbasid state, such as Mosul and Baghdad. Admittedly, the latter continued to retain its status as a political, scientific, and philosophical capital; nevertheless, it could not have become such a vibrant intellectual hub without drawing upon a sufficiently broad reservoir of scientific expertise in its surrounding regions, particularly the expertise that made it possible to establish, renew, and sustain over time the various *bīmāristāns* in which Ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī practiced. This observation invites us to qualify the overly globalizing judgments usually made about the supposed “scientific decline,” and instead to emphasize the need for a nuanced analysis attentive to the regional and local specificities that condition the actual vitality of scholarly milieus.

That said, it seems to us that scientific activity reached its peak—or at least came very close to it—on the eve of the Crusades and the multiple political crises that shook Baghdad. Admittedly, certain regions of the Abbasid state were already experiencing a marked slowdown, or even an abrupt cessation, of intellectual activity—as was the case for part of the Fertile Crescent and, most notably, for al-Andalus. Indeed, it appears as though the gradual decline of these two major centers, during an initial phase situated precisely around the turn of the twelfth century, contributed to the stimulation and revitalization of scientific centers in neighboring regions: the Maghreb to the west, Egypt at the center, and Persia to the east.

It nevertheless remains to be understood why and how, in a second phase, the disappearance of several major hubs ultimately came to affect the vitality of those that endured. This question remains open, and in light of the paucity of genuinely multidisciplinary research devoted to the history of intellectual activities in the Islamic world, it seems unlikely that fully satisfactory answers will be reached in the near future.

A second question, which naturally arises once the scope and significance of the contributions of Abū l-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī are fully appreciated, concerns the reception of his ideas and works. This issue relates in particular to their dissemination and impact in Baghdad and, more broadly, within other scientific centers of the Islamic world. Here again, it must be acknowledged that the answers remain partial and largely incomplete, especially with regard to the traditions of natural philosophy and physics, among other fields.

The mechanisms through which knowledge circulated often invoked in connection with trade, pilgrimage to Mecca, or scholarly travel (education, learned encounters, attendance at schools and teaching institutions)—remain, for these specific domains, insufficiently documented and inadequately analyzed. This situation calls for more systematic and in-depth future research, in order to achieve a clearer understanding of the modes of transmission and reception of Ibn Malkā's thought within the Islamic world at the time of the apogee of the Muslim state.

As for the possible circulation of the writings or ideas of Abū'l-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī beyond the borders of the Muslim state, this issue has been the subject, for more than half a century, of assertions, hypotheses, and ongoing questions. It must first be emphasized that even if we confine ourselves to the Muslim world, we have found, to date, no reliable evidence attesting to the actual presence of this scholar's works in Egypt or in the western Islamic lands, with the exception of al-Shām (the Levant), where traces appear in certain written sources.

Moreover, even in cases where such circulation may have occurred, the ideas and methodological approaches of Abū'l-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī did not encounter the conditions necessary for their assimilation and further development. This stands in contrast to other bodies of work, particularly those devoted to the philosophical interpretation of physics in the traditions of Ibn Sīnā (Avicenna) and Fakhr al-Dīn al-Rāzī, which benefited from more favorable intellectual contexts and sustained reception.

That said, it is entirely conceivable that scientific writings in Hebrew or Arabic (or portions of their contents) may have circulated directly from

al-Andalus to certain intellectual centers of medieval Europe, without passing through the traditional circuits of Dār al-Islām. This hypothesis has been proposed and defended here and there, particularly in an attempt to account for the extent of the correspondence between Abū'l-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī and his contemporary Abraham Ibn Ezra. However, to date, we possess no reliable historical evidence that would allow this conjecture to be confirmed beyond the existence of exchanges limited to theological questions within Judaism.

The third question, even more ideological in nature, concerns the issue of the conversion of Abū'l-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī from Judaism to Islam—a topic that has deeply divided historians for more than a century. The accounts that have come down to us, fragmentary and at times contradictory, have given rise to three main interpretations: some scholars regard this conversion as an established fact, fully assumed by Ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī; others, adopting a more cautious stance, cast doubt on it or consider it insufficiently substantiated by the available sources; still others view this very doubt as a historiographical construction shaped by power relations, arguing that narratives minimizing or contesting the conversion are motivated by a desire to exclude the possibility that it may have been prompted by fear rather than by sincere personal conviction.

These divergent positions each supported by sometimes contradictory sources, occasionally stemming from the same historian call for a critical reassessment grounded in a rigorous analysis of the political, social, and religious context in which Abū'l-Barakāt Hibat Allāh ibn Malkā al-Baghdādī lived and worked. Ultimately, it remains to be clarified to what extent the accounts at our disposal reflect historical reality or, on the contrary, the narrative strategies of scholarly milieus concerned with preserving idealized representations, alternately, of the Jewish community or of the Islamic intellectual elite of his time. Here again, in the absence of in-depth research drawing upon other disciplines, it seems unlikely that these ambiguities will be definitively resolved in the immediate future.

Pending even partial answers to the three questions already outlined concerning the scientific centers of the Muslim state and the forms of their preservation after the XIII^e century—it is nevertheless possible, starting now,

to undertake a comprehensive study of Ibn Malkā's oeuvre. Such an endeavor would both complement existing studies devoted to specific aspects of his writings and contribute to a clearer understanding of his role as a scholar in the development of scientific ideas in the Islamic world.

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